

HOW TO GIVE FEEDBACKS TO YOUR STUDENTS?

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Abstract

Being a teacher is not only teaching and assisting students. They have the responsibility to know the correct way of giving feedback because the feedbacks may influence students to study more or make them feel disappointed. Many scientists shared a lot of ideas on this topic, but they all come to the same conclusion that future teachers should know how to criticize their students' abilities and give appropriate feedback.

How to Give Feedback to Your Students?

I. Why do students need feedback?

Is it for only improving students' mistakes or something better? It is much deeper than you can assume. It is a way to motivate learners to do their best, become self-regulated learners, be confident and develop their skills. Meaningful feedback can greatly enhance their learning and achievement. However, the way to use feedback also has crucial importance.

On August 6, 2014, the writer named Marianne Stenger wrote in her research that Professor James Pennebaker from the University of Texas at Austin has been researching the benefits of frequent testing and the feedback it leads to. He explains that in the history of education, the role of feedback has always been central: "When people are trying to learn new skills, they must get some information that tells them where they were not correct and where they should make some changes. Classroom learning is no exception." She said: "Both the mastery of content and, more importantly, the mastery of how to think to require trial-and-error learning."

The drawback is that not all feedback is equally effective, and it can even be counterproductive, especially if it's presented in a solely negative or corrective way.

II. What are the most effective ways to use feedback in education?

Although, there is not a quick or easy answer to this question. The five research-based tips which Marianne Stenger informs for providing students with the kind of feedback that will increase motivation, build on existing knowledge, and help them reflect on what they have learned.

1. Be AS SPECIFIC AS POSSIBLE

In a review of the available research titled “The Power of Feedback,” University of Auckland professors Helen Timperley and John Hattie published on March 1, 2007. They highlight the importance of equipment learners with specific information about what they are doing right or wrong.

For instance; feedback like “Great job!” doesn’t tell the learner what he did right, and likewise, a statement such as “Not quite there yet” doesn’t give her any insight into what she did wrong and how she can improve it in the next time around.

Otherwise, researchers suggest being an accurate person and taking the time to provide learners with information on what exactly they did well, and what may still need improvement. They also note that it can be helpful to tell the learner what he is doing differently than before. Has a student’s performance changed or improved since the last time when you assessed her? Teachers have to report it, even if he still has a long way to go.

2. THE SOONER THE BETTER

Multiple studies indicate that feedback is most effective when it is given as soon as it is possible, rather than a few days, weeks, or months down the assignment. The study looked at delayed versus immediate feedback, by Front Hum Neurosci. Published online 2011 February 1st. the learners who were given immediate feedback showed a significantly larger increase in execution than those who obtained deferred feedback.

Another research, from the University of Minnesota, by S. Jay Samuels Yi-Chen Wu, showed that students were able to better comprehend the material they had just read by taking immediate feedback.

The researchers wrote;” It may not always be possible to provide students with feedback right on the spot, but sooner is better than later.”

3. Commentator should pay attention to THE LEARNER’S ADVANCEMENT TOWARD A GOAL

Timperley and Hattie note that effective feedback is most often focused on specific achievements that students are working on(or should be working toward). When providing feedback to students, it should be clear how the information they receive will help them move towards their ultimate goal.

4. PRESENT FEEDBACK CAREFULLY

The way feedback is presented can affect how it is perceived, which means that sometimes even the most well-intentioned feedback can be perceived incorrectly and reduce the motivation of the student.

Edward Deci, psychologist and author of many types of research has identified three situations in which feedback could be counterproductive(1991).

A situation when students feel too strictly monitored: If learners feel that they are being too closely under the control, they might become nervous or self-conscious, and as a result, disengaged from learning.

When students interpret feedback as an attempt to manipulate them: It may sometimes interpret feedback as an attempt to control students or tell them how they have to do something, rather than giving instructions on how to improve their mistakes

When learners feel an uncomfortable sense of competition: Feedback shared in a group setting could cause learners to feel like they have to compete with their peers. This can be another source of disengagement in learning.

When teachers speak negatively about students to a large number of people, and students experience an unpleasant feeling of rivalry, feedback shared in a group setting can make students feel that they have to compete with their classmates. This can be another source of learning detachment.

If situations will be avoided, Edward Deci suggested fully explaining the purpose of any monitoring and ensuring that learners were able to fully understand how the feedback is meant to help them compete against their personal bests rather than each other.

5. PERSUADE LEARNERS IN THE PROCESS

It is impossible to overestimate the value of involving learners in the process of collecting and analyzing performance-based data. According to Pennebaker, “students must have access to information about their performance... At the most basic level, students need to know whether or not they have mastered the material. Giving them information about how they study, read, search for information, or answer questions can be extremely beneficial.”

When students have access to this information, they become more conscious of their learning, are better able to spot faults, and eventually build solutions for dealing with weak points.

It will be more productive when a teacher uses the connected words to increase students' motivation or likewise diminish it. For example; positive feedback like (I like it! that's it! or that's correct!). After positive feedback commentator should continue with negative such as (Not exactly, Good try but..., and Unfortunately not.) finally conclude with encouraging feedback (I am impressed, that is much better, and so on).

To sum up, providing learners with correct and meaningful feedback plays an important role in students' future assignments. Students may fall into

depression or even lose interest to study when a teacher does not know how to give the right comments. To avoid this situation, future teachers should learn how to be able to criticize students' abilities and have an idea of how to give correct feedback.

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